

THE ROLE OF PARLIAMENT IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

This scientific article analyzes the role of the national parliament based on the reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan. A scientific assessment of practical activities to achieve the UN Sustainable Development Goals in Uzbekistan is provided.

Key words

parliament, Oliy Majlis, Uzbekistan, UN, sustainable development goals, reforms.

Our country renewed its membership in the organization on October 13, 2017, all this time the Oliy Majlis has been closely cooperating with the largest international structure. With the republic gaining independence, our national parliament, as one of the most important institutions of state power, began to develop on the basis of democratic principles. As the highest legislative body, it developed and adopted laws aimed at strengthening the sovereignty of the state and deepening democratic, socio-economic reforms in society.

If we look at the history of the formation of parliaments in developed countries, we can highlight the peculiarities in the social and state structure of each individual country, national traditions, legal culture and the political will of the people.

In recent years, when, under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the processes of further liberalization and reform of all spheres of life of the state and society are accelerating, the role and importance in the socio-political life of the country of representative bodies elected by the people - the parliament, local Kengashes of people's deputies - is increasing[1].

The Parliament of Uzbekistan has always supported all humanitarian initiatives of the UN and programs developed in this direction, and actively participated in their implementation.

At the first meeting of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, the President of Uzbekistan proposed that the Legislative Chamber should start

hearing reports of ministers on the implementation of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

It is known that the UN Sustainable Development Goals program until 2030 was adopted. Due to the fact that the economic, social and environmental issues raised in this program are of great importance for the development of our country, by the joint decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis, the Parliamentary Commission was formed in February of this year to monitor the implementation of the national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030[2].

In this regard, for the first time in the history of the Oliy Majlis, a meeting of this commission was held with the participation of representatives of international organizations, and the representatives of the international organizations who participated in it specifically emphasized that this commission was formed and its work plan was approved in order to fulfill the goals of sustainable development in the conditions of the coronavirus pandemic, and that our country should be an example for other countries. During the six months of this year, a number of committees of the Legislative Chamber heard the reports of the relevant state administration bodies on the implementation of the national goals and tasks of the BRM within the framework of parliamentary control, and the decisions of the committees were adopted.

Along with this, an international conference dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the adoption of the Charter of the United Nations by the Oliy Majlis under the heading "UN 75th Anniversary: Looking to the Future" was held on the topic "Uzbekistan and the UN: Cooperation in the Achievement of Sustainable Development Goals", in which UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres sending his sincere greetings to the participants, he said that the international community fully supports the initiatives of Uzbekistan to ensure peace and international harmony in the world.

It is known that the government of Uzbekistan regularly submits its report to international organizations regarding the provision of human rights and freedoms. The important thing is that the opinions and conclusions of these organizations are very important and have a great impact on the prestige of Uzbekistan in the international arena[3].

In March 2020, Uzbekistan submitted the Fifth Periodic Report on the implementation of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights by the Government of Uzbekistan to the United Nations. On the conclusion of this report,

a parliamentary hearing was held in the Legislative Chamber in the form of a video conference.

The noteworthy point of this report is that in the Fifth Periodic Report of the Government of Uzbekistan by the UN Committee on Human Rights, in the direction of ensuring the rights and interests of women, examining draft laws adopted in the field of gender equality, protecting motherhood and childhood, strengthening the institution of the family, and Human Rights The implementation of the previous recommendations of the committee by Uzbekistan was recognized as a great achievement. Such a positive conclusion is very important for Uzbekistan. Because, when other countries want to cooperate with our country, they first of all study how people and their rights are ensured, and take into account the recommendations of international organizations in this regard.

It is known to all of us that further improvement of the existing mechanisms in the field of human rights, conducting its effective monitoring, coordinating the activities of state bodies and civil society institutions, will ultimately have a direct impact on increasing the authority of the state in the international arena[4].

Based on this, in May of this year, for the first time at the plenary meeting of the Legislative Chamber, the Republic of Uzbekistan decided to harmonize the country's legislation with international legal norms in the field of human rights and freedoms, in particular, on the implementation of personal, political, economic, social and cultural rights and freedoms of citizens. the information of the National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the state of compliance with international obligations was heard in the form of a parliamentary hearing.

Taking into account the recommendations of international organizations, UN chartered bodies and treaty committees, organizational measures for the establishment of a parliamentary commission to monitor compliance with international obligations in the field of human rights based on the Decree of the President "On approval of the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Human Rights" is being implemented.

Today, the Oliy Majlis has approved "roadmaps" in this direction regarding the protection of human rights, and systematic monitoring of their implementation is being carried out. One of them is the "roadmap" for ensuring freedom of religion and belief, approved by the joint decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The special importance of this issue is that until 2017, no representative at the UN level came and studied the situation in this field in our country. That is why the special rapporteur of the UN Human Rights Council on the issue of freedom of

religion and belief A. Shahid visited Uzbekistan for the first time in 2017 and personally studied this issue. Based on its final recommendations, "roadmaps" are adopted by our parliament every year and their implementation is monitored.

In a video conference dedicated to this issue, the implementation of the "roadmaps" developed to ensure freedom of religion and belief in the conditions of the coronavirus pandemic was controlled by the Parliament of Uzbekistan. It was positively evaluated by Shahid and representatives of major international organizations in the world.

On June 30, 2020, in connection with the widespread celebration of the International Day of Parliamentarianism, an online international parliamentary forum was held in the Legislative Chamber on the topic "The role of the parliament in the implementation of the recommendations of the UN's charter and treaty bodies on the example of the UN Human Rights Council and the Human Rights Committee."

At the forum, leading experts and experts of the UN gave a speech on the protection of human rights, and they recognized that Uzbekistan is improving the legislation on the implementation of the recommendations of the UN Human Rights Council as a positive achievement.

In conclusion, the noteworthy aspect of these online events is that the Legislative Chamber is organizing its activities based on the principle of openness in terms of ensuring human rights and freedoms. In addition to increasing its international influence, it also strengthens the confidence of the country's citizens in the parliament.

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